
IS THIS INSECTAGEDDON? A DECADE'S INFLUENCE OF GLOBAL WARMING ON INSECT DIVERSITY IN AN INTACT POND

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ABSTRACT: In terms of global warming's impact on aquatic regions and biodiversity, insect losses are an example that was recently defined as insectageddon. Türkiye is one of the most important countries in terms of abundant biological diversity and contains a very high number of ecosystem types. To investigate the outcome of these colossal warming risks, the composition and distribution of insects were examined for the first time in a mild glacial-intact pond between 2012-2022. The aim was to determine how this catastrophic influence affects the community structure of insects in an intact aquatic pond. Additionally, measurements of water temperature (w. temp), dissolved oxygen (DO), pH and electrical conductivity (EC) play an essential role in the biological monitoring of this global warming effect. In total, 20 species of Coleoptera and 5 species of Hemiptera were collected. Results emphasize the potential danger to ecosystem functions by converting the dynamics to species level.

KEY WORDS: Aquatic insect, biodiversity, freshwater, global warming, Türkiye

Ecosystems are very important to humans (Schowalter et al., 2018). Aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems have similarities and differences among ecosystem types (Chase, 2000). The aquatic one of these two ecosystems are dynamic systems involving the balancing of processes between aquatic biological communities and environments (Liao & Huang, 2014). Freshwater is central to society and the environment (Naiman & Turner, 2000), while every aquatic organism has a range of environmental options (Cairns et al., 1975).

Aquatic environments are highly vulnerable (Spacessi, 2013) to permanently damage from a growing number of human induced changes (Liao & Huang, 2014). This makes these areas increasingly fragile, even more so in the context of climate change (Wongchuig et al., 2018; Escanilla-Minchel et al, 2020). Climate change drives stressors that shape ecosystems (Birk et al., 2020) and this change has become a hot topic and an alarming issue for freshwater systems worldwide (Duchenne-Moutien & Neetoo, 2021).

Freshwater is among the most widespread ecosystems in the world and the majority of the 126,000 freshwater animal species are insects (60.4%) (Fenoglio et al., 2016). Therefore, providing solutions to some environmental issues may be possible by researching aquatic organisms (Prather & Laws, 2018). Although there are genotypic differences in the abilities of subpopulations of freshwater insects to cope with varying parameters (Williams & Williams, 1998). These insects may be considered model organisms to analyze the framework and function of freshwater ecosystem because of their high abundance, high birth rate

with short generation time, large biomass and rapid colonization of freshwater habitats (Choudhary & Ahi, 2015). They can provide reliable information about habitat and lake sustainability (Bektaş, 2020), and they respond to changes in their environment (Qadir & Malik, 2011). However, diminishing diversity is causing a massive decline in insect abundance (Ehlers et al., 2021).

The temperature of the Earth's surface is a very important determining factor for climatic conditions (Sorokhtin, 2006). The impact of climate change on uncontaminated, remote and intact aquatic areas is a mystery. Little is known about some ecological dynamics in more intact ecosystems (Fashing et al., 2014); for instance, subglacial lakes are high-priority for scientific investigation due to crucial questions which require a focused interdisciplinary approach to the study of these environments (Rack, 2016). In this case, it has increased the interest in intact areas.

Also, community alterations will greatly increase the accuracy and power of environmental risk assessment to protect wildlife and ecosystems from disturbance by chemical contaminants. Some contaminants change ecosystems and can have both direct and indirect impacts on multiple levels of organisms (Saaristo et al., 2018). In accordance with this aim, for the first time in an uncontaminated and intact area, the aim was to monitor the indirect effects on aquatic insects in terms of quantitative distribution, global warming, insect diversity and number in the intact region. Because of the intact ecosystem and seasonal variability, freshwater systems (floating island) are an ideal setting to examine insect and other macroinvertebrate diversity.

Abiotic factors such as electrical conductivity (EC), temperature (w. temp), pH, dissolved oxygen (DO) etc. were shown to influence bioavailability (Avenant-Oldewage and Marx, 2000). Cabrera et al. (2021) emphasized the lack in-depth knowledge about both taxonomic and functional diversity, complementary to biological and chemical substances, in the aquatic area of the Amazon.

Simple ecological and quantitative scans make insect loss (defined as insectageddon) beneficial as a mapping tool for environmental monitoring and can provide a low-cost and low-impact solution to environmental issues. Freshwater systems undergo some changes based on the relationship between formation and temperature of subaqueous substances (Ohsawa et al., 2010) and other physical and chemical data. Some previous studies provided the inspiration for our study. Long-term observations can prove that the populations of aquatic settings also change. Unlike other studies, correlations of insect losses and changes in ecological parameters were monitored for the first time during a decade-long follow-up in an intact (pilot area) area.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study area and collection of insect samples

The study area is located in Erzurum (Fig. 1). The region has continental climate in general. Zökün (pond) floating island was chosen because the influence of global warming on aquatic insects was firstly investigated in a small intact pond that is easily monitored and researched. This wetland is a pond with coordinates 40°15'55' and 40°38'37' and an average altitude of approx. 1953 meters. It formed on an old landslide and is small pond with length 71 m and width 38 m (Karahan et al., 2011). Samples were taken from six different points in this pond

(Table 1). The pond is intact due to being far from settlements and is mild-glacial due to high altitude.

Figure 1. Location of the selected research area in Türkiye.

Table 1. Description of sampling sites.

Location /Zökün pond	Long; Lat	Altitude (m)	Water height (m)	Predominant substratum	Description of Sampling Point
Point 1	40°15'55'' 40°38'37''	1953	0.1	Mud	Anthropogenic activities almost nonexistent. There are cow digestion residues as a result of traditional livestock farming.
Point 2	40°15'54'' 40°39'34''	1952	0.1	Mud	Anthropogenic activities almost nonexistent. There are cow digestion residues as a result of traditional livestock farming.
Point 3	40°15'57'' 40°38'37''	1953	0.2	Mud	Anthropogenic activities almost nonexistent. There are cow digestion residues as a result of traditional livestock farming.
Point 4	40°15'55'' 40°38'35''	1953	0.2	Mud+Sand	Anthropogenic activities almost nonexistent. area with very little sand but vegetation.
Point 5	40°15'50'' 40°38'36''	1954	0.3	Mud	Anthropogenic activities almost nonexistent. area with very little sand but vegetation.
Point 6	40°15'50'' 40°38'38''	1953	0.3	Mud	Anthropogenic activities almost nonexistent. There are cow digestion residues as a result of traditional livestock farming.

Since aquatic insects are sensitive to environmental factors, they are generally easily sampled, and their ecology and taxonomy are relatively well known (Nilsson & Holmen, 1995), they are potentially suitable bioindicators. Coleoptera and Hemiptera are known to be diverse in rare and unique ecosystems (Turić et al., 2012). A lot of aquatic insects, such as Coleoptera and Heteroptera, were suggested as indicators of biodiversity in inland waters (Mellado, Velasco & Millán, 2006; Turić et al, 2012). They are easily collected (Hilsenhoff & Tracy, 1985). Additionally, the author separated individuals belonging to Hemiptera and

Coleoptera on genus level, and even some families on species level, which was also effective on selection of these two orders.

Aquatic insects (Coleoptera and Hemiptera) were collected with standard sieves with 3.15 x1 mm pores (mesh size 500 µm) in all seasons except winter (due to not being found in the winter) between 2012 and 2022 from the intact ponds in Tortum, Erzurum province, Türkiye (Figs. 1 and 2). These macroinvertebrates from each unique location were placed in separate small plastic bottles, were firstly killed with ethyl acetate and stored in the bottles in the research area, containing 96% ethanol to reach a final concentration of 70% ethanol. After sorting, these samples were cleaned with a brush before identification, and then the aedeagus of the beetles was dissected under a stereo microscope in the laboratory. Collected insects were identified using identification keys developed by Bektas et al. (2014), Bektas (2015), Bektas (2018), Bektas et al. (2019), Darılmaz & Kıyak (2009), Daşbaşı (2017), Kasapoğlu (2002), Martins-Silva (2022), Mitra et al. (2016), Önder & Lodos (1986), Smetana (1985) and Yalçın (2010). Identification was made at family, genus and species level, respectively. Unidentified samples were recorded at genus level.

Figure 2. Images of study (winder and summer area and collecting of insects).

Chemical parameters

Water quality indices were used to assess spatial and temporal changes and classify water quality in wetlands (Kannel et al., 2007). These indices, which were used in this study, are w. temp, DO, pH, and EC. These parameters were measured on site with a portable device (Table 2). Measurements were made directly in the water body. Results were reported instantaneously.

Table 2. Water quality parameters, digital used during 2012–2022 for surface waters of Zökün ponds.

Parameters	Abbreviation	Units	Analytical methods	Instruments
Water temperature	Wtemp	°C	Digital	portable device
pH	pH	–	Digital	portable device
Dissolved oxygen	DO	mg.L ⁻¹	Digital	portable device
Electrical conductivity	EC	µS.cm ⁻¹	Digital	portable device

Statistical analysis

Shannon-Wiener diversity index was used for each sample. The scale of species diversity and richness was calculated using the natural logarithm. In terms of species abundance:

$$H = \log_e N - \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} (p_i \log_e p_i) n_i$$

where n_i = the number of species with i individuals. Data measures were applied per individual according to Anonymous (2023). Obtained data were codified and entered into Microsoft Excel software, then uploaded to Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS 22.0) software and analyzed using statistical methods. Diversity of aquatic insects and relationships with chemical parameters were correlated using this program (Fig. 4).

RESULTS

Freshwater systems are crucial for all land-based wildlife, they are used in versatile ways and have great economic and conservation value (Beklioglu et al., 2010). Freshwater fish, aquatic insects and mollusks are among aquatic animal groups (Li et al., 2022). Life is impossible without freshwater as it is very important for all living creatures in the world (Bhat et al., 2019). Inland waters are often considered to be hot spots of biodiversity (Gopal et al., 2001; Williams et al., 2004); for example, ponds provide useful models to show how evolution enables interim segregated populations to utilize small ecosystems (Cayrou & Cereghino, 2005). These freshwaters are important for many aquatic and semi-aquatic species and flooded wetlands are often rich in nutrients and provide habitats for aquatic insects (Waterkeyn et al., 2008). Animal populations are characterized by increased natural mortality; however, trends of variation in reproductive parameters along with ecological gradients are still unclear (Zadubrovskaya et al., 2020).

This study aimed to assess the diversity and presence of aquatic insects and their relationship with some ecological parameters during ten years in the research area. The insects were collected from seven different points in a single location. The study recorded 25 species of aquatic insects belonging to 2 orders and 13 families. Presence and diversity of aquatic insects, unfortunately, tended to decrease during the decade.

Insect populations are complex open biological systems with nonlinear dynamics (Stankevych et al., 2019) and climate warming may indirectly affect population dynamics (De Senerpont Domis et al., 2013). In this context, the target

was to examine diversity of Coleoptera and Hemiptera species; collection, monitoring and reporting of these species between 2012 and 2022 were performed to monitor individuals belonging to these macroinvertebrate groups. In eleven years of monitoring, it was noted that Hydrophilidae and Noteridae individuals were more common among Coleoptera, while Notonectidae family was noted in Hemiptera order. In terms of individuals, 63 individuals from Hydrophilidae, 20 from Dytiscidae, 3 from Gyrinidae, 1 from Haliplidae, 17 from Helophoridae, 3 from Hydraenidae, 1 from Spercheidae, and 11 from Noteridae were reported. In the Hemiptera order; 1 individual from Belostomadiae, 3 from Nepidae, 3 from Gerridae, 5 from Notonectidae and 1 from Pleidae were confirmed. Members of other orders were not found, dubious groups and most individuals identified were returned to the pond to preserve ecological sustainability.

A total assessment based on chemical and biological indices was used to evaluate the pollution status of rural ponds, which also stores rainwater in rainy seasons (Liu et al., 2022). Therefore, measures should be taken to improve the water quality, habitat conditions and biotic community of rural ponds, especially in severely polluted rural ponds in Zökün floating islands (mild-glacial, intact ponds). Because aquatic insects are plentiful in most freshwater habitats and often exhibit high diversity (Hershey et al., 2010), biomonitoring based on aquatic insects plays a significant role in assessing the environmental status of these aquatic regions (Priyanka & Prasad, 2022).

Most insects are species abundant, ecologically dominant (Chapman & Bourke, 2001), cold-adapted (Spitzer & Danks, 2006) and rich in biodiversity (Heino, 2009). Consequently, properties of aquatic insect populations make it more likely for these specimens to dominate biomonitoring samples (Orlofske & Baird, 2014). The purpose of this study was to indicate the human impact on intact ponds based on abiotic and biotic (macroinvertebrates) presence and diversity. Here, water chemical characteristics and macroinvertebrates (some aquatic insects) were examined and results were obtained.

Data about essential abiotic variables are presented in table 4. Wtemp varied from 10.1 °C to 24.2 °C, due to differences in the time of sampling (early morning or midday). Correlations of DO, EC and pH with each parameter were calculated in table 4. The lowest oxygen concentration was observed in more recent years.

Aquatic insects are ideal organisms to analyze freshwater ecosystems due to their high abundance and large biomass (Choudhary & Ahi, 2015). With this logic, this study analyzed and presented the 11-year distribution of aquatic insects in table 3 and figure 3. However, a strong relationship between chemical parameters and insect biodiversity must be revealed. At non-metric multidimensional scaling, the importance of abiotic factors was revealed by the data (Fig. 4).

Table 3. Diversity of aquatic insects at each year.

Collected Insects		Sampling time (year)											Total	
Family	Species	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022		
Coleoptera	Hydrophilidae	<i>Helochares lividus</i>	1	1	NF	2								
		<i>Microlaccobius g. gracilis</i>	3	2	NF	1	2	NF	1	1	NF	1	1	12
		<i>Laccobius simulatrix</i>	NF	2	NF	2								
		<i>Laccobius syriacus</i>	4	3	NF	3	4	NF	5	NF	1	1	1	22
		<i>Laccobius sculpus</i>	NF	1	NF	1								
		<i>Laccobius sulcatus</i>	NF	1	NF	1								
		<i>Hydrochara caraboides</i>	NF	1	NF	1								
		<i>Enochrus fuscipennis</i>	3	1	1	NF	1	1	NF	NF	2	NF	1	10
		<i>Coelostoma orbiculare</i>	1	2	1	1	NF	5						
	<i>Anacaena lutescens</i>	1	NF	NF	NF	1	1	1	1	NF	NF	1	6	
Dytiscidae	<i>Agabus</i> spp.	NF	2	3	NF	NF	NF	2	NF	NF	1	1	9	
	<i>Deronectes</i> spp.	1	NF	1	NF	1	NF	1	NF	NF	NF	NF	4	
	<i>Hydroglyphus</i> spp.	2	NF	1	1	NF	1	NF	1	1	NF	NF	7	
Gyrinidae	<i>Gyrinus</i> spp.	1	1	1	NF	3								
Halipidae	<i>Pelodytes</i> spp.	NF	1	NF	1									
Helophoridae	<i>Helophorus armeniacus</i>	1	1	4	1	1	2	NF	NF	1	NF	NF	11	
	<i>Helophorus brevipalpis</i>	NF	NF	NF	NF	1	1	1	2	NF	NF	1	6	
Hydraenidae	<i>Ochthebius</i> spp.	1	1	NF	1	NF	3							
Spercheidae	<i>Sperchus</i> spp.	NF	1	NF	1									
Noteridae	<i>Canthydrus</i> spp.	5	NF	1	1	1	NF	NF	1	1	NF	1	11	
Belostomatidae	<i>Lethocerus</i> spp.	NF	1	NF	1									
Nepidae	<i>Nepa</i> spp.	NF	1	NF	1	1	3							
Gerridae	<i>Aquarius</i> spp.	1	1	1	NF	3								
Notonectidae	<i>Notonecta</i> spp.	NF	1	1	1	1	NF	NF	1	NF	NF	NF	4	
Pleidae	<i>Plea</i> spp.	NF	NF	NF	NF	1	NF	NF	NF	NF	NF	NF	1	
Total number of individuals		25	25	15	10	14	6	11	7	6	4	8	126	
Total number of species		13	19	10	8	10	5	6	6	5	4	8	94	
Average Population Size		1.92	1.31	1.5	1.25	1.36	1.00	1.83	1.16	1.2	1.0	1.0	5.2	
Simpson Index		0.04	0.02	0.0	0.06	0.06	0.00	0.16	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.06	

Table 4. Mean, minimum (Min.), maximum (Max.) and standard deviation (Std) of measured scales in average of 6 sampling points throughout 11 years.

Variable	Unit	Mean	Min.	Max.	Std.
Water temperature (W.temp)	°C	17.8	16.1	22.0	1.59
Dissolved oxygen (DO)	mg.L ⁻¹	8.0	8.3	8.9	0.69
pH	-	7.1	6.8	7.9	2.5
Electrical conductivity (EC)	µS.cm ⁻¹	557.5	78	884	94.9

Individual numbers of families in the aquatic Coleoptera by years

Individual numbers of families in the aquatic Hemiptera by years

Family distribution of collected insects between 2012-2022

- Hydrophilidae**
Helochares lividus,
Microleucobius g. gracilis,
Laccobius simulatrix,
Laccobius synacus,
Laccobius scultus,
Laccobius sulcatus,
Hydrochara caraboides,
Enochrus fuscipennis,
Coelostoma orbiculare,
Anaena litescens
- Dytiscidae**
Aqabus spp.,
Deronectes spp.,
Hydrolyphus spp.,
Gyrinidae
Gyrinus spp.
- Helophoridae**
Helophorus armeniacus,
Helophorus brevipalpis,
Hydraenidae
Ochthebius spp.,
Noteridae
Canthidrus spp.
- Belostomidae**
Lethocerus spp.,
Nepidae
Nepa spp.,
Sperchidae
Sperchus spp.
- Gerridae**
Aquarius spp.,
Notonectidae
Notonecta spp.,
Pleidae
Pleq spp.
- Dytiscidae**
Aqabus spp.,
Deronectes spp.,
Hydrolyphus spp.,
Gyrinidae
Gyrinus spp.
- Hydrophilidae**
Helochares lividus,
Microleucobius g. gracilis,
Laccobius simulatrix,
Laccobius synacus,
Laccobius scultus,
Laccobius sulcatus,
Hydrochara caraboides,
Enochrus fuscipennis,
Coelostoma orbiculare,
Anaena litescens
- Belostomidae**
Lethocerus spp.,
Nepidae
Nepa spp.,
Sperchidae
Sperchus spp.
- Gerridae**
Aquarius spp.,
Notonectidae
Notonecta spp.,
Pleidae
Pleq spp.

Figure 3. Distribution of collected samples at the level of family and genus (some of them on species level) in the process.

Figure 4. Correlation graphics of EC, pH, DO and W.temp. according to collected insects.

DISCUSSION

Climate change caused by the human population is influencing freshwater ecosystems (Palmer et al., 2009; Ebersole et al., 2020). This anthropic impact on water bodies has been a focus of research for over 100 years (Kuznetsov & Petrov, 2017) and there are different levels of impact depending on severity, temporality, persistence, and possible treatment. A major goal and challenge is to understand the responses of these areas to a world changing due to many human impacts. However, there is a need to implement conservation and mitigation strategies that maintain the structure and function of these ecosystems and their benefits to society (Beklioglu et al., 2016). Meanwhile, these small areas provide a wide variety of resources that have economic value (Chase & Ryberg, 2004; Hanson et al., 2005; Ruggiero et al., 2008), since they are important habitats for the maintenance of biodiversity (Oertli et al., 2005). Where some ecosystems persist, it is usually because extreme environmental conditions in small watersheds restrict both alien invaders and human use (Moyle, 2014). There is lack of thorough knowledge about the taxonomy and ecology of regional aquatic insects (Priyanka & Prasad, 2022). Knowledge from further studies in these areas will gradually advance our understanding of population dynamics. This is logistically tractable and repeatable but requires long-term monitoring. Because of the loss of insects, the seasonal fluctuation in temperature (Tanamura & Hirose, 2017) may result in an accompanying loss of plant species that depend on insect pollination (Ehlers et al., 2021). In light of this information, minor impacts due to diffuse or isolated pollution occur, such as in isolated mild-glacial small ponds. Protection

of intact aquatic areas, even if mild-glacial, is pivotal for success of adaptation strategies for aquatic ecosystems. These abovementioned phenomena are key for taking actions.

Human activities may influence the diversity of aquatic insects in ponds. For a long time, it was hypothesized that monitoring an intact pond may illustrate how global warming will affect these regions. Floating islands are accepted as islands due to being in a water body as well as being surrounded by water (Bulut, 2023). This zone was selected based on different geographic localization and ecological characteristics. Therefore, the priority of the research area was discerned, because it is very far from settlement and there is no pollution, so it is possible to examine the impact of climate change and global warming alone. Also, this floating island (an intact pond, Zökün pond) has facilities available to collect data and insect species, which were other factors affecting selection of the prototype research area. Among abiotic and biotic metrics used to indicate multi-stressor effects, the use of benthic invertebrates is frequently applied in some aquatic studies (Nöges et al., 2016). These scales were used for freshwater assessment studies in intact ponds. Analysis of diversity-presence of some aquatic insects and some ecological parameters indicated unstable community composition and distribution.

Macroinvertebrate (some aquatic insects) community composition in a pond is expected to be explained better by long-term monitoring. For community ecological data, there is a unimodal response of species abundance to environmental gradients (Benejam et al., 2008). Insects provide critical resources for fish and wildlife production and their products are valuable food resources in many cultures (Schowalter et al., 2018), so effects of some ecological parameters on freshwater ecosystems were investigated by examining a number of organisms (Simeonov & Chirila, 2006), so insects have a very large impact among living organisms, both in terms of numbers and efficiency (Bektaş et al., 2022).

A decade-along observation of chemical parameters in water showed the influence on population dynamics. Variations in species composition through the years reflected recent species introductions and peaks in the abundance of some species (Drapeau Picard et al., 2021). In this study, when the distribution of the families according to year is examined, some insect individuals were present throughout the research period, some individuals were very rare, and some family members that were most likely to be caught were not found at all. Due to the small area and cold weather conditions, few insect individuals were caught. In addition, in order not to manipulate the ponds, individuals with suspicious identification and outside the research orders (Coleoptera and Hemiptera) were left alone (Fig. 3). Coleoptera has 176 families, 29,500 genera and 386,500 species. Four suborders of Coleoptera are Archostemata, Myxophaga, Adepfaga and Polyphaga. The suborder Polyphaga includes more than 90% of the Coleoptera species. The families Spercheidae, Helophoridae, Hydrophilidae, and Hydrochidae that were subjects in our study belong to the Polyphaga suborder. Gyrinidae, Halplidae and Noteridae families belong to the Adepfaga suborder. Helophoridae family has 192 species worldwide and 52 species are known in Türkiye. Hydrochidae family includes species worldwide and 8 species are known in Türkiye. Hydrophilidae family has 2932 species worldwide and 103 species are known in Türkiye. Gyrinidae family has 750 species belonging to 13 genera worldwide and 11 species are known in Türkiye. Halplidae family has about 200 species belonging to 5 genera worldwide and 16 species are known in Türkiye. Noteridae family has 250 species belonging to 14 genera worldwide and 3 species

are known in Türkiye (Darılmaz & Kıyak, 2009; Darılmaz & Incekara, 2011; Glime, 2015; Bektaş, 2018). Spercheidae is widely distributed globally (Shepard & Chaboo, 2015). This family has 18 species around the world, and two species are known in Türkiye (Darılmaz & Kıyak, 2011). Hemiptera families, known from Türkiye, include Alydidae, Belostomatidae, Coreidae, Corixidae, Gerridae, Nepidae, Notonectidae, Piesmatidae, Rhopalidae, Saldidae and Stenocephalidae (Yıldırım et al., 2013). The number of species in the Hemiptera order was described as 42,347 around the (Henry, 2009). Aquatic individuals are also adapted to different types of habitats such as water surface, interior of water and intertidal zones (Schuh & Slater, 1995). The number of species recorded in Türkiye is more than 1500 (Kıyak, 2016; Çerçi & Koçak, 2016). Nepoidea superfamily generally has high numbers of species (like some Belostomatidae). These predatory insects live in lentic habitats or in calm parts of streams, sometimes in silt or the mud at the bottom. There are 8 genera and 35 species in the Palearctic region (Yıldırım et al., 2013).

Studies about altitude and sex-ratios in previous thesis studies and research-articles were carried out and some of the studies attempted to summarize Coleoptera and Hemiptera in graphic form (Bektaş, 2018). The outcome of this study observed that *L. syriacus* species did not decrease in number over time, but there was a decrease in other species. *Microlacobius g. gracilis*, *Laccobius syriacus*, *Enochrus fuscipennis*, *Agapus* spp., and *Helophorus hilaris* (Coleoptera) individuals are notable. A reduction in the number of individuals should not be considered as only due to global warming, but there is high probability that there can be no other reason for this decrease in an intact region. For this reason, this study shows the impact of this warming on an intact pond that can be considered a glacier, even if it is a very small numerical change. Quantitative differences in Notonectidae (Hemiptera) family members was noted. One individual was caught in the families Nepidae, Gerridae, Notonectidae and Pleidae. Additionally, Corixidae, Cydninae, Ochteridae, Naucoridae, Veliidae, Leptopodidae, Hydrometridae, Hebridae and Mesoveliidae, which are known from Türkiye were not found. Nevertheless, long-term observations are necessary to explain the elusive reasons for ecological losses. These reasons are insufficient taxonomic data (usually families), lack of general descriptive information for many species, and lack of existence of a standardized methodology for recording species losses.

At each sample point, ecological parameters such as w. temp, DO, pH and EC were measured using portable device. Some parameters have overriding influence on distribution of plankton (exo-macroinvertebrate but related to them) in freshwater settings, which indicates that the aquatic region is still very productive in terms of providing food organisms for higher aquatic life (Arimoro et al., 2018). Also, these parameters were chosen because they can be measured directly and instantly thanks to portable devices. At the same time, integration of abiotic-biotic data and analysis of factors affecting water was proven to be an important mechanism for monitoring, evaluation and determination of future environmental protection. Here, this study provides the methodological and technical basis for some variables such as abiotic and biotic (aquatic invertebrates) factors. When it is taken into account that Zökün pond has an altitude of approximately 2000 meters (1950 m), it is inevitable to consider extreme conditions. Aquatic zones in high mountain areas involve extreme environmental conditions such as low temperatures (Sahin & Barınova, 2022).

Apart from the metal content in aquatic substances, several other environmental factors such as w. temp, pH, DO, and EC in wetlands also affect the presence of aquatic insects (Prommi et al., 2014). Some insect orders are often found in clean waters and are very sensitive to changes in water chemical parameters (Chun et al., 2017). In view of DO measurements, in recent years, even in this mild-glacial and intact pond, it affected insect diversity, despite the minimal level. Diversity of aquatic insects, particularly Coleoptera and Hemiptera orders, tended to be higher at higher DO levels. Considering chemical parameters of w. temp, DO, pH and EC and insect numerical-diversity distribution, there was no significant change in water temperature. But it was observed that the DO ratio decreased very slightly in parallel with the decrease in insect diversity. Although there were seasonal differences in pH changes, there was no significant difference.

Signal value of a taxon is better at the species or species group level than at the genus level. Some genera include many species with very different ecological preferences (Butler et al., 1999). In extreme conditions, a new perspective has emerged showing that genus-species of insects can be identified and can be caught at any time, and that numerical distributions can illustrate the impact of global warming in mild-glacial areas in the long term. Hence, it is suggested that researching both mild-glacial and intact ponds may be more suitable for influence of this warming than shallow lakes. There is an ongoing unprecedented loss of insects in present times (Barmantlo et al., 2021). These losses have led to widespread monitoring of ongoing insect dynamics globally. Correlation analysis showed no effect of DO and pH in the pond on the presence of aquatic insects (Fig. 4).

Shannon Diversity Index (H) mean value was 2.84. It was realized to have an average in terms of diversity, in spite of the fact that it has slightly decreased in value. Correlation values; EC: -0.54, pH: 0.01, DO: 0.06 and w. temp.: -0.64. EC and W. temp. is an opposite relationship between these parameters and the number of individuals collected. There is almost no positive relationship with pH value. However, it was observed that there was a slight positive correlation in the DO values. Between 2011 and 2022, the richness of individual-species was, respectively, 13,12,11,11,10,9,6,6,5,5,4,9. Nonetheless, it is thought that there may be an increase in the value of wealth in 2022 as a result of the fact that the factories, which cause environmental pollution due to the covid-19 epidemic, are not in operation for 2 years (Table 5). It is seen that the difference in EC value is considered to be due to excessive rainfall (Anonymous c, 2023). This is probably related to differences in results obtained in detailed studies in more extensive large lakes containing heavy metal content and with much longer-term research.

In short, a deeper integration of disciplines and development of broader realistic approaches is needed to understand and predict present and future global change (Gerhard et al., 2022). Because insect biodiversity assists researchers in interpreting the dynamics of some habitats (Spitzer & Danks, 2006), monitoring multiple-chemical scales (e.g., EC, DO) and developing macroinvertebrate diversity and expanding potential variables among biotic and abiotic factors.

Finally, this study also shows that even if minimal, there was a relationship and mild correlation between abiotic and biotic factors. At the end of this study, vulnerability is quite evident even in small ponds. It is highly recommended to integrate global warming management strategies even for intact ponds in Türkiye,

and to create a platform to continuously inform and educate researchers about potential warming hazards and impacts in such areas.

Table 5. Species richness during collecting.

CONCLUSION

The influence of global warming on aquatic insects was investigated for the first time in an intact small pond that was easily monitored and researched. Data indicate appreciable effects of this huge phenomenon (warming). The advantage of long-time monitoring of a wetland shows that impacts may not only occur in known shallow lakes, but also occurs in intact aquatic regions. Changes to aquatic insect populations will have important implications for prediction of invasive or endangered species and potential ecosystem mechanisms. Future adaptation of macroinvertebrate diversity in ponds will extend the yield of aquatic ecosystem products sustainably while ameliorating climate change impacts in aquatic regions. Furthermore, additional research is needed to provide more data to investigate insect communities and underlying dynamics and interactions.

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